

COMPARING THE EFFECT OF SELF-EFFICACY BELIEFS ON ENGLISH LEARNING WITHIN METHODOLOGICAL PLURALISM

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Abstract:

This study attempts to determine the effect of self-efficacy beliefs on English preparatory students' existing capacities via the use of quantitative and qualitative methods within methodological pluralism (a combination of meta-analysis, descriptive survey, and qualitative document analysis plus action research). In the quantitative phase of the research, both meta-analytic method and descriptive method were used. In the meta analytic method, the Comprehensive Meta-Analysis statistical program was used to compute the effect size values of the included studies (N= 12) with the pretest-posttest control group model and carried out between 2000 and 2017 in national and international level. In the descriptive research of the study, the English Self Efficacy Beliefs Scale was used on English preparatory students (N= 117) to determine the effect of self-efficacy beliefs on their language skills. In the qualitative part of the study, data collected both through document analysis (N=7) from the included studies and through semi-structured interviews applied to English preparatory students (N= 58) were analysed via the Maxqda 11 program. The quantitative and qualitative results of the study are consistent and suggest that while self-efficacy beliefs on English learning is high, in terms of using the four skills, listening and speaking are the ones that the participants exhibit the weakest self- efficacy beliefs respectively.

Keywords: self-efficacy, meta-analysis, thematic analysis, Maxqda program, methodological pluralism

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1. Introduction

Self-efficacy, which is as a part of social cognitive theory and an approach to perceiving intellectual development, refers to beliefs in one's capacity to overcome a task (Bandura, 1997). Individuals' beliefs in their capabilities influence their performance immensely (Bandura, 1997). After the concept of self-efficacy was introduced in 1977 by Bandura, many educational studies rotated around one notion and stressed that self-efficacy is an inevitable part of learning (Doordinejad & Afshar, 2014). According to Bandura (1986), the sources such as mastery experience, vicarious experience, persuasions, and physiological states lead to develop the efficacy beliefs. Bandura (1997) clarifies the most effective source of self-efficacy beliefs as mastery experience. To him, while success increases self-efficacy, failure undermines it. Vicarious experience is related to achieve one's a task when seeing the similar performance of others around him/her that achieved the same task (Bandura, 1997). Verbal persuasion is encouraging and convincing a person verbally to have the ability to perform the given task (Bandura, 1997). Physiological and emotional states such as anxiety, fatigue, and nervousness can influence self-efficacy. Negative thoughts, for example, lead to inadequate performance and failure by doubling one's stress (Pajares, 2002).

In the second and foreign language acquisition area, the role, if any, of self-efficacy has not been exactly determined due to being still obscure or partly explored areas because of language learning strategies, and self-efficacy (Gahungu, 2009). However, self-efficacy has been regarded as a strong predictor in success of language learners (Chen, 2007).

1.1 The Aim and Significance of the Study

A great number of studies have investigated the role of self-efficacy beliefs and their effects on different language learning and teaching environments. However, the literature review of this study from national and international publications reveals that less experimental research has focused on self-efficacy beliefs in the context of foreign language learning. Researchers aimed to investigate the impact of self-efficacy on English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners' English learning process (i.e. Baleghizadeh & Masoun, 2013; Khanmohammad & Eilaghi, 2013; Rathert, 2013; Semiz, 2011) on EFL learners' reading comprehension (i.e. Alimoradi, Jahandar & Khodabandehlou, 2013; Ekiz, 2013; Kassem, 2013; Salehi & Khalaji, 2014), on EFL learners' speaking skills (i.e. Aregu, 2013; Gol & Aaleabbas, 2016), on EFL learners' writing skills (i.e. Balaman-Uçar, 2016; Yavuz-Erkan, 2004), on EFL learners' vocabulary learning (i.e. Noroozi & Mehrdad, 2016) and, on EFL learners' listening skills (Zareian,

Adel & Noghani, 2015). Despite the popularity of self-efficacy and its effect in foreign language education, relatively few studies provide an in depth analysis of self-efficacy in EFL learning. In this regard, although Raoofi, Tan and Chan (2012) investigated self-efficacy beliefs from a theoretical point of view in the context of foreign languages rather than English through a narrative review method, no meta-analytic studies have been reported on the effect of self- efficacy or the foreign language programs' effect on self-efficacy beliefs of English language learners in EFL learning setting. Therefore, the meta- analytic phase of this study aims to contribute to the literature and the related field by identifying, evaluating, and summarizing the findings of all relevant individual studies over both EFL programs' effect on self-efficacy beliefs of students and self-efficacy and its effects on English teaching/ learning as a foreign / second language, thereby making the available evidence more accessible to decision makers.

On the other hand, this study attempts to combine methods within methodological pluralism in order to achieve reliable research results. In this vein, while both meta-analytic and descriptive- methods were used in the quantitative phase of the research, both thematic and action research methods were used in the qualitative phase the study. By the integration of diverse methods in this study, it is aimed to enhance a holistic understanding of the topic and to present a more comprehensive and remarkable results.

To determine the self-efficacy beliefs of the preparatory students on their existing capacities and abilities for organizing and implementing the behaviors that are expected from them toward English contributes to the regulation of learning environments in terms of coping with learning difficulties, development of foreign language skills and professional preparation. Therefore, students' attitudes toward learning will move forward in a positive process and toward the higher goals they have set for themselves. In this regard, it is aimed to determine the English self-efficacy beliefs of the preparatory students studying at the School of Foreign Languages and to address these beliefs in terms of variables such as gender, graduated high school, reasons for university preference and the order of preference. On the other hand, it is also aimed to combine the data acquired both quantitatively and qualitatively from the preparatory students with the data obtained through meta-analysis and thematic analysis phases of this research to perform the multiple analysis.

Within the frame of the purpose of this study, the following questions were searched:

1. What is the effectiveness of self-efficacy on EFL students' academic achievement in terms of effect sizes (ES) calculated from the recent research?

2. What are the students' views, which are available in the studies included in the meta-analytic part of this research, on their English self-efficacy beliefs and on the factors that may affect their beliefs positively or negatively?
3. What level of self-efficacy beliefs do the preparatory students studying at the School of Foreign Languages have regarding English reading, writing, listening and speaking skills?
4. Do the English self-efficacy beliefs of the preparatory students vary according to the variables such as gender, graduated high school, reasons for university preference and the order of preference?
5. What are the views of the preparatory students studying at the School of Foreign Languages on the factors affecting their self-efficacy beliefs toward English?

2. Material and Methods

This research is a mixed methods study within the scope of methodological pluralism, both quantitative and qualitative methods were used to reveal the effect of self-efficacy beliefs of the preparatory students on their existing capacities and abilities for organizing and implementing the behaviors that are expected from them toward English in order to cope with learning difficulties, development of foreign language skills and professional preparation. A combination of quantitative and qualitative methods in mixed model designs can increase the strengths of each approach (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Additionally, enriching the methodology of the research not only develops more entire and integral understandings (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011) but also provides validity and reliability in the researcher's findings (Creswell, 2003).

This research consisted of a 4-step process. In the quantitative phase of the research, the meta-analytic method and descriptive research were used respectively. In the qualitative phase, thematic analysis and action research were conducted and the data were analyzed using the Maxqda 11 program.

2.1 Quantitative Study - Meta-analysis phase of the study

The first phase of the study included Meta-analysis. The meta-analytic method is a statistical technique to combine the findings of independent studies dealing with the same issue (Crombie & Davies, 2009).

2.1.1 Literature search procedure

It was attempted to include all the experimental studies related to the effect of foreign language programs on self-efficacy beliefs and the development of language skills of

foreign language learners by searching the studies carried out between 2000 and 2017 at international and national areas within the Higher Education Council National Thesis and Dissertation Center (YOK), ProQuest Dissertations and Theses (PQDT), Google Scholar, Ebscohost-Eric, Ebscohost-Professional Development Collection and, Sage Journals Online search engines. As a result of the literature search, a total of 12 studies (8 articles, 1 MA thesis and 3 Ph.D. dissertations), where pre-test and post-test in particular were implemented and comparisons were made amongst groups using the selection criteria of the study, were selected out of 32 studies.

2.1.2 Introducing a set of inclusion criteria

Various eligibility criteria included studies with pretest/ posttest research designs, providing enough statistical information including sample sizes, means and standard deviations to calculate effect sizes and published within the period 2000 -2017.

2.1.3 Data Analysis

The Comprehensive Meta-Analysis (CMA) statistical program was used in data analysis. In the estimation of effect size, Hedges'd formula was utilized (Hedges & Olkin, 1985). Additionally, the (Q-statistic) chi-square (χ^2) heterogeneity test with degree of freedom (k-1) to test whether there was heterogeneity between the studies, fixed effect models (FEM) and random effects models (REM) to determine the effect sizes were used. Afterwards, the statistical data were changed into a common effect size and evaluated using Thalheimer and Cook's (2002) guidelines.

2.2 Qualitative Study - Thematic analysis

The second phase involved thematic analysis which is used in qualitative research and focuses on identifying, analyzing and reporting themes within data by detailed reading, generating the initial codes, combining codes into overarching themes (Braun & Clarke, 2008). Accordingly, the detailed examination of the studies concerned with the factors affecting participants' efficacy beliefs in a foreign language teaching/ learning through document review based on content analysis was performed using the Maxqda 11 program.

2.2.1 Data Analysis

Seven (2MA theses, 2 PhD theses, and 3 articles) of the 12 studies involving the participants' opinions on the self- efficacy and English teaching/ learning were examined in order to obtain data from document analysis and were utilized to reach the qualitative data for thematic analysis. These studies, which were coded, for example, as

T1p.41 (T: thesis; 1: thesis number; p41: the page number of the quotation in the PDF), A2p4 (A: article; 2: article number; p4: the page number of the quotation in the PDF) were transferred into the computer and the studies included in the thematic analysis were arranged and saved as [(Aregu, 2013)_{A2p.105}, (Ekiz, 2013)_{T3p.58}, (Özkasap, 2009)_{T4p.61}, (Semiz, 2011)_{T2p.96}, (Uçar & Yazıcı-Bozkaya, 2016)_{A7p.23}, (Yavuz-Erkan, 2004)_{T1p.119}, (Zareian, Adel & Noghani, 2015)_{A8p.268}]. Then, all transcripts were entered into Maxqda 11 program, qualitative software for data management, coding and analysis and the data analysis occurred.

2.3 Qualitative Study - Action Research Design

The third phase involved a qualitative study, action research design, to reveal the views of the preparatory students studying English Language Teaching and English Language and Literature (N= 58) studying at Cumhuriyet University School of Foreign Languages in the Fall term of 2016-2017 academic year and selected by maximum variation sampling. The aim of using maximum variation sampling, a purposive sampling technique, is to gain greater understandings into a phenomenon by looking at it from all angles (Erdoğan, 1998). An interview form for the data collection tool was developed by the researcher in the light of review of literature and experts (1 Associate Professor and 2 Assistant Professors of Educational Sciences, and 3 instructors who teach English as a foreign language). In addition to personnel information such as gender, open-ended questions were included in the interview form. With the open ended questions, students were asked to indicate positive or negative views on their English language level and the use of the four skills equally as a preparatory student, difficulties encountered in practice stemming from teachers or students and, their suggestions.

2.3.1. Data Analysis

Each participant's responses to each question were coded as P5-M/F (P: Participant; 5: Participant No; M: Male/F: Female). Then the responses were categorized into theme and code models through the examination of the transcribed verbatim scripts in Maxqda 11. The emerging themes were identified as (1) The suitability of English language level that the students have already had for a preparatory class (2) The use of the four skills equally, (3) Problems stemming from teachers and students and, (4) Suggestions. Codes related to these themes were generated from particular words and phrases of the participants.

2.4 Quantitative Study - Descriptive study

In the fourth phase, descriptive research method was performed. Descriptive research is used to describe a situation in the past or still existing in the present as it is (Karasar, 2009). In this sense, the preparatory students studying at the Foreign Language School

of Cumhuriyet University were asked to complete “The English Self Efficacy Beliefs Scale” developed by Hanci Yanar and Bumen (2012).

2.4.1 Population & Sample

The population of the study regarding the fourth phase consisted of 223 English preparatory students studying at the Foreign Language School of Cumhuriyet University in the Fall term of 2016-2017 academic year. However, the sample of the study contained 117 (91 female and 26 male) preparatory students selected voluntarily and accepted to participate in the study. Distribution of the sample according to variables is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of Preparatory Class Students Taking Part in the Sample According to Variables

Variables		N	%
<i>Gender</i>	Male	26	22.2
	Female	91	77.8
Graduated High School	Anatolian Teacher High School	6	5.1
	Anatolian High School	89	76.1
	Anatolian Technical-Vocational High School	9	7.7
	Regular High School	13	11.1
The order of preference at the university admission	1-5 preferences	45	38.5
	6-10 preferences	24	20.5
	11 and above preferences	48	41.0
Reasons for preference	Being my choice	84	71.7
	Being my family’s choice	7	6.0
	The guarantee of having a job	12	10.3
	In order not to be idle	14	12.0
Total		117	100

2.4.2 Data Collection

“The English Self Efficacy Beliefs Scale” developed by Hanci Yanar and Bumen (2012) was used to measure the English self-efficacy beliefs of the students. This is a 34 –item and 5- point Likert scale having four sub-dimensions, namely, reading, writing, listening and, speaking and ranging from 1 (Completely Disagree) to 5 (Completely Agree). It is a valid and reliable instrument to measure English self-efficacy beliefs with 0.97 of the Cronbach’s alpha coefficient (Hanci Yanar & Bumen, 2012).

2.4.3. Data Analysis

In the analysis of data, the SPSS 18.0 package program was used for descriptive statistics. In addition, independent sample t-test, ANOVA when the dependent variables were normally distributed according to the result of the homogeneity of variances, and Kruskal Wallis H test for the non-parametric items test were also used.

3. Findings

In this section, the quantitative and qualitative findings of the study are given separately. It is aimed to identify supporting or contrasting points by blending the quantitative and qualitative findings.

3.1 The Findings of Meta-analysis phase of the study

The general effect size findings of the 12 studies (8 articles, 1 MA thesis, and 3 Ph.D dissertations) that met the inclusion criteria of this study were given in Table 2. Related to FEM computation, the standard error was 0.073 and the upper limit for 95% of the confidence interval was 1.074, the lower limit was 0.7489 and the effect size was 0.932, which is a large level according to Thalheimer and Cook's (2002) classification. Furthermore, Z test calculations revealed statistically significant at .01 level ($z= 12.798$; $p=0.000$). As a result of the homogeneous test, the Q statistical value was computed to be 51.014. In a 95 percent significance level from the chi-square table, the approximate critical value of 11 degrees of freedom is accepted as 19.68. Therefore, Q statistical value of 51.014 was found to exceed the critical value of chi-square distribution at 11 degrees of freedom ($\chi^2(0.95) =19.68$) and thus, the distribution of the effect sizes according to FEM was determined to be heterogeneous and the analyses were carried out according to REM (see Table2).

Table 2: The Distribution of Homogeneous Values, Average Effect Sizes and Confidence Intervals for the Studies Included in the Meta-Analysis Based on the Effect Models

Model Type	n	Z	Q	ES	SE	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Limit	Upper Limit
FEM	12	12.798	51.014	0.932	0.073	0.789	1.074
REM	12	6.187	5.6802	0.958	0.153	0.646	1.261

$P_{FEM}: 0.00$ $p_{REM}: 0.00$

As seen in Table 2, according to REM computation, the standard error was 0.153 and while the upper limit for 95% of the confidence interval was 1.261, the lower limit was

0.646. The effect size was 0.958, which shows a “large” level of compliance according to Thalheimer and Cook’s (2002) classification. In accordance with the z- test calculation result, the statistical significance was 6.187 (p=0.00). The Q statistical homogenous test value for the 12 studies was calculated as 5.6802. Therefore, as the distribution of χ^2 with regard to 11 degrees of freedom with Q statistical value of 5.6802 did not exceed the critical value of 19.68, the homogeneity of effect-size distribution was accepted according to the REM.

3.2 The qualitative findings of the study - Thematic analysis phase of the study

The participants’ views that are available in the included studies on the factors affecting their self-efficacy beliefs in EFL learning /teaching were examined using document analysis of the studies. The responses were categorized under two headings: “The views of the participants on the factors affecting ELT students’ self- efficacy beliefs positively” (Figure1) and “The views of the participants on the factors affecting EFL students’ self- efficacy beliefs negatively” (Figure2).

3.2.1 The views of the participants on the factors affecting ELT students’ self- efficacy beliefs positively

Figure 1 presents the codes related to the factors affecting foreign language students’ self-efficacy beliefs positively as “having much confidence in learning English, “seeing learning English as a future goal”, “wish of applying for the ERASMUS program”, “Wish of living abroad”, “Receiving positive feedback from teachers on their constantly increasing skills”, “Having above-grade-level achievements in the class and making great strides in academic standings”, “Being a pleasant student and accepting responsibilities”, “Being eager to filling their spare time with English”, “Having a great attitude toward learning English and showing outstanding progress”, “Being a creative thinker and readily grasping new information quickly”, “working well with others” and “doing well in class”.

Figure 2: The views of the participants on the factors affecting ELT students' self-efficacy beliefs positively

In this regard, a quotation from the T4p.58 coded study, *I really have much confidence in learning English. ...I can comfortably speak English, and I can easily communicate with foreign people. However, in order to fully practice speaking, I definitely need to live in a foreign country for a while* and A2p.105 *I feel that my speaking skills is somewhat good ..., and I feel happy when I speak* can be referenced to the codes related to “having much confidence in learning English” and “Wish of living abroad”. Similarly, the quotations taken from the T4p.58 coded study such as *...This [learning English better] is important for me and it is a goal that needs to be achieved as I am planning to apply to a graduate program.... and then to go to America in the following summer to practice. For this reason, I am thinking about applying to the ERASMUS program* led to the emergence of the codes “seeing learning English as a future goal” and “wish of applying for the ERASMUS program”.

3.2.2 The views of the participants on the factors affecting foreign language students' self-efficacy beliefs negatively

The themes related to “the views of the participants on the factors affecting foreign language students' self- efficacy beliefs negatively” were generated as: (1) Factors

stemming from students, (2) Factors stemming from outside of students, and (3) Factors stemming from teachers' performance (See Figure 2).

As seen in Figure 2, the codes regarding the factors stemming from students and affecting their self-efficacy beliefs negatively toward learning a foreign language were aligned as "Lack of effort", "Laziness", "Lack of ability - seeing himself / herself not having an ability to learn a language", "Lack of strategy", "Lack of interest", "Fear of being caught while making mistakes", "Fear of pronouncing words differently", "An emotional block from the previous years toward learning English", "Not liking English", "Studying the exams only one night before", "Having the idea that learning from a foreigner is more instructive" and, "Not having an idea how to seek and create opportunities to use the language". Quotations from the T4p.65 coded study *I don't make an effort to do these things [to learn, remember, and study the information presented in class and in the materials]. English and I are two different worlds* emphasize the lack of afford and ability.

The codes related to the theme "Factors stemming from outside of students" were emerged as (1) Teachers' high expectations and concerns for students, (2) Insufficient listening and speaking lessons, (3) Being speaking and listening classroom tasks' superficial, (4) Ineffective language instruction, (5) Teachers' being fast in teaching in prep class, (6) Lessons' become too difficult for students to follow easily, (7) Difficulty in passing criteria, and (8) Teachers' not being able to activate motivation of students. The attributions of high expectations of teachers such as *Our expectations of them are greater. Since we know what each student do or not do individually, we have high expectations and concerns* prevailed in some included studies (e.g. A5p.549). Additionally, a quotation from the T2 p.96 coded study, *the teachers are fast in teaching. I just can't keep up with the teachers. For example, the teacher is writing a few words on the board and explaining them in English which I can't understand...* mentioned a negative contribution of fast teaching to the learner's performance. In some studies the participants seemed mostly to blame teachers when they failed in learning a foreign language and explained their failure as being the fault of the teachers or ineffective language instruction. For example the quotation from the T2 p.95 coded study: *..The reason is I didn't find what I expected here [The student has shared her disappointment with the education given in the preparatory program]. I was initially so willing to learn English. But I don't know. ..When the teacher asks questions, I dare not look at him in case he calls me. I am not successful* indicates that the main reason behind the failure of students is based on teacher and preparatory program.

Figure 2: The views of the participants on the factors affecting ELT students' self-efficacy beliefs negatively

The codes related to the third theme, namely, "factors stemming from teachers' performance that affect learners' self-efficacy beliefs negatively (from teachers' own perspectives)" were: (1) Not having good education on listening and speaking at university, (2) Having speaking anxiety because of being a non-native speaker, (3) No need to improve English when working at state schools although being always a room for improvement in private schools, (4) Although being qualified enough to teach grammar and writing, being weak in teaching listening and speaking skills because of not having a chance to practise it, (5) Fear of making grammar mistakes, (6) Lack of in-service training, (7) Some teachers' being young and inexperienced at the beginning of their career, and (8) Not developing interesting materials to become successful in attracting the students' attention. Some attributions of graduation with inadequate education on speaking and listening from the T4p.61 coded study such as *I find myself strong in teaching grammar and writing, but I sometimes find myself weak in teaching listening and speaking skills because I can't find much chance to practice it indicate that although instructors had an education on speaking and listening at university, they still find it*

insufficient for themselves to put into practice. Another quotation from the T4p.58 coded study, *We all know the disadvantages of being a non-native teacher, but we don't know the advantages of it. If necessary, these things should be taught us with in-service trainings* reveals the need and importance for in-service training for foreign language teachers especially in improving their speaking and listening skills.

3.3 Qualitative Findings of the Study - Action Research Design

The views of the preparatory students (N=58) studying at Cumhuriyet University School of Foreign Languages in the Fall term of 2016-2017 academic and selected by maximum variation sampling concerning the effect of self-efficacy beliefs of the preparatory students on their existing capacities and abilities for organizing and implementing the behaviors that are expected from them toward English in order to cope with learning difficulties, development of foreign language skills and professional preparation were collected through semi-structured interviews. Then coded, analyzed and modeled. Four themes were identified as (1) The suitability of English language level that the students have already had for a preparatory class (2) The use of the four skills equally, (3) Problems stemming from educators and students and, (4) Suggestions. They were modeled and illustrated in Figure 3 and 4 with related codes.

3.3.1 The suitability of English language level that the students have already had for a preparatory class

The two emerged subcategories regarding the first theme, namely, the suitability of English language level that the students have already had for a preparatory class were “Positive views stemming from having the ability to successfully accomplish the required academic tasks” and, “Negative views stemming from the feeling of having inadequate English” (See Figure 3).

As given in Figure 3, the codes regarding the positive views included “Having the necessary knowledge and skills to accomplish English successfully in preparatory class”, “Being willing to enhance their knowledge of English”, “Being self-confident and skilled in using English”, “Having the ability to use English for communicative purposes” and “Loving English”. In this vein, a participant (P28/F) stated, *I study hard, I know I can do. ... I do my best, because I like English...* The participant P32/M asserted *I think I'm not good at English. I make many mistakes in my exams. However, I have some confidence in my pronunciation and communication in English and I feel better about myself that I can accomplish English soon.* The codes emerged from the negative views were “Insufficient education due to being given much more weight to the grammar lessons than the other ones”, “Not sufficiently and thoroughly understood the contextual

knowledge every time”, “Insufficient vocabulary knowledge”, “Insufficient opportunities to speak English in lectures” and, “Thinking Turkish in English classes”. In this regard, a participant (P15/F) emphasized on creating opportunities to use the target language, and added, *we have limited opportunity to use English. In class, most students direct to teachers to speak Turkish rather than English. That’s why, teachers rarely speak English.*

Figure 3: The suitability of English language level for a preparatory class

Another participant (P39F) stressed on the weight given to grammar and continued *I think teaching grammar of English is exaggerated much more than other skills in Turkey. On the other hand, although I do the revision of grammar subjects that we have learnt at home regularly, it doesn’t help me speak effectively in public without practicing speaking skills.*

3.3.2 Views of the participants regarding the use of the four skills equally

The codes emerged from the positive and negative thoughts of the participants in the frame of the theme, “Views of the participants regarding the use of the four skills equally” were given in Figure 4.

Figure 4 shows the views of the participants based on the use of the four skills equally. The codes regarding the positive contributions of using each skill equally consisted of “Being strongly correlated to each other”, “In spite of being distinct enough, contributing each skill to overall communicative ability”, “Improving self-confidence”, “Increasing the willingness to participate in the courses”, “Building positive attitudes toward the use of English in all aspects”, “Increasing motivation and keeping it high”, “Increasing the desire to learn”, “Arousing curiosity and interest throughout a lesson”, “Enhancing productivity in all English based courses”, “Enabling learning enjoyable and fun”, “Increasing the willingness to participate in the course”, “Allowing the training of more qualified students”, “Providing quick learning opportunity”, “Overcoming learning barriers”, “Preventing misconceptions”, “Saving the time” and, “Ensuring access to learn easily.”

Figure 4: Views of the participants regarding the use of the four skills equally

Related to high demand for communicative skills, a participant (P2/F) stated *giving an equal opportunity to develop each skill that is strongly correlated to each other, regardless of receptive or productive skills, provides learners with skills, experience and confidence*. Similarly, another participant (P46/F) added *Using the activities that incorporate all four skills in the class will provide us with opportunities to develop each skill effectively*. On the other hand, negative codes included “Not given equal weight to each skill in schools during their education”, “Insufficient teaching of listening and speaking skills”, “Insufficient oral English output”, “Not being forced to speak English in lectures”, “Insufficient time allocation for each skill”, “Insufficient instructional aids”, “Not being exposed to native speaker teachers of English” and, “No being exposed to native speaker teachers of English”. Most participants (i.e. P12/M, P18/F, P21/F, P27/M, P32/M, and P43/M) thought that learning from a foreigner is more instructive and effective. They emphasized the importance of correct pronunciation that can only be done by native speakers and implied that they are eager to learn English by hearing and listening to it more than from following the books of grammar. Similarly, the participant P57/F stressed the importance of having a native teacher as *I'd prefer myself to learn English from a native person whose language flows and not from someone who just knows the rules*.

3.3.3 Problems stemming from educators and students

The codes regarding the theme “Problems stemming from educators and students” emerged separately and given in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Problems stemming from educators and students

The codes regarding the problems stemming from educators were aligned as “Insufficient visual aids”, “Using more textbook activities and materials than any other supplementary activities”, “Having book based speaking courses”, “Teachers’ speaking Turkish in classes”, “Teachers’ obliging students with the correct answer each time instead of giving positive encouragement”, “Boring course contents such as numbers and scientific topics”, “Teachers’ not having more fun”, “Teachers’ not creating engaging speaking tasks”, “Not encouraging every student, especially introverts, to class participation”, “Giving unnecessary and monotonous homework”, “Ineffective listening activities”, “Not providing effective feedback to enhance performance in the class”, “Being too tedious to use textbook materials very often”, “Not being enthusiastic about the material selection”, “Passing the other activities quickly”, “Giving the activity as homework”, “Continuing the same activity in the other lesson”. In this regard, a participant (P38/M) stated, *In the listening and speaking course, it is too boring to study from a textbook. Instead, I’d prefer teachers to use diverse materials rather*

than follow a textbook to expand our capacity. On the other hand, a shy student (P54/F) complained about being perceived by teachers as lacking in effort or interest in lessons and continued I'm an introverted student and feel uncomfortable speaking in a group setting. Therefore, I'm misunderstood by my teachers. However, although my contribution in class is extremely limited, I'm good at English academically and it is my preference to be quiet in class. Regarding the code "Giving unnecessary and monotonous homework", a participant (P39/F) stated Due to being given repetitive and monotonous homework, I do my homework as fast as possible whether it is correct or incorrect. To me, in case the teachers check it, doing homework incorrectly is better than not doing the homework at all. The codes regarding the problems stemming from students emerged as "Insufficient lesson revision", "Indifference", "Lack of motivation", "Lack of many of the prerequisite skills and knowledge", "Students' not knowing what's best for their own learning", "Insufficient vocabulary", "Not listening to the teacher carefully during the lesson", "Reluctant learners due to their unwilling choice of this field" and, "Heavy homework load". A participant (P13/F) emphasized insufficient practice skills and added I don't leave plenty of time to revise all of my subjects. I generally do last minute cramming for my exams. Similarly, some participants (P11/F, P36/F and P57/F) stressed that due to insufficient attention, or focus, they don't remember things easily. A participant (P32/M) expressed I have a belief that I will be much more disciplined and highly motivated this year than before but somehow with a sense of desperation, I don't get round to it.

3.3.4 Suggestions

The codes for the theme suggestions, which were given in Figure 6, included "Teachers should be able to eliminate problems related to maintaining class discipline", "Teachers should create a classroom environment to promote oral language of students", "Persistent use of Turkish should be avoided during activities such as speaking, listening, and pronunciation", " Teachers should set rules about tardiness and should set penalties for students who break them", "Students should pay extra time and attention to master the subject matter", "Struggling students should be encouraged to take extra effort", "Teachers should choose listening or reading material that interests students and will hold their attention", "To better understand the material, teachers should allow students to know a bit about what they are going to listen to or read", "To develop students' vocabulary and comprehension, teachers should know that a great way is more emphasis on speaking and listening activities", "Teachers should make students' listening and reading actively rather than passively", "Since students are not supposed to understand every word, teachers should have students try to make a guess based on the context without using the dictionary too much", "Teachers should help

students use their new language skills very often”, “When choosing texts, teacher should consider not only their difficulty level, but also their interest or their humor”, “Teachers should be capable of making teaching and learning curve fun”, “Teachers should change the idea that mostly foreign language students identify having a native teacher as a model of perfection and as an advantage while identifying a non-native speaker teacher as inadequate or less favorable to teach the foreign language.”

Figure 6: Suggestions

In this context, a participant (P38/M) stressed the importance of the classroom environment in which the teacher has the control to promote student engagement and added *Through the effective monitoring of students' progress during the lessons, teachers can contribute to success in learning English in a classroom environment.* By the same token, another participant (P19/F) stated *Teachers should not only set classroom rules to foster learning such as not to speak Turkish during the lesson, to be on time and present, and etc.. they should but also set penalties for students who break them...* Regarding the suggestions for listening and speaking tasks, a participant (P48/F) recommended daily use listening and speaking activities and continued *Teachers should give us the opportunity to listen and speak different topics and situations that we can use in our real world actively.* Another participant (P51/M) pointed out the importance of motivating students and stressed

Teachers should motivate students with good techniques such as offering extra credit points or praising them for contributing an answer.

3.3. The Quantitative Findings of the Study - Descriptive analysis phase of study—

After performing the statistical analysis of the English Self Efficacy Beliefs Scale, arithmetic mean and standard deviations of the items obtained from this study are given in Table 3, 4, 5 and 6 respectively.

Table 3: Arithmetic Mean and Standard Deviations Obtained for Each Item Regarding Reading

Item	Reading	Mean	SD
1	I can understand when reading an English text	3.91	.82
2	I can understand important points when reading English academic texts	3.20	.88
3	I can visualize what I read in my mind	3.87	.96
4	I can find the theme or the main idea of the English text that I read	3.82	.92
5	I can answer questions about an English text	3.64	.88
6	I can guess the words that I do not know the meaning when reading an English text	3.25	.94
7	I can easily find the information I am looking for in an English text	3.49	1.01
8	I believe that I will be successful in reading sections of English exams	3.50	1.04
Average		3.59	.97

The participants' views on the items regarding the subscale reading are at the Agree Level on the 5 –point Likert scale, with a mean of 3.59 ($SD = .97$). The views of the participants on the item 2, namely, *I can understand important points when reading English academic texts* and on the item 6, namely, *I can guess the words that I do not know the meaning when reading an English text* were at the Somewhat Agree Level with the means of 3.20 and 3.25 ($SD = .88; .94$) respectively. This result remarks that students are pretty good at understanding, visualizing, interpreting and answering the questions of an English text. However, they are moderately good in understanding important points and guessing the unknown words in an English Text.

The mean scores and standard deviations of the items regarding the subscale writing are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Arithmetic Mean and Standard Deviations Obtained for Each Item Regarding Writing

Item	Writing	Mean	SD
1	I can write a good paragraph or an essay	3.20	.90
2	I can use the grammar rules correctly when writing a paragraph or an essay in English	3.39	.89
3	I can use punctuation correctly when writing an English text	3.48	1.02
4	I can fully and clearly express my thoughts when writing an English text	3.35	.94

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5	When I cannot write something in English, I try to solve the problem instead of giving up	3.74	1.15
6	I can highlight important points when writing English	3.48	1.01
7	I can rewrite an English text with my own words	3.22	1.09
8	I can express myself in English in daily life (Resume, application form, complaint letter, etc.)	3.75	.98
9	After writing anything in English, I may notice my mistakes	3.51	.85
10	I need help when doing activities related to writing in English	3.01	1.08
Average		3.41	1.01

The data show that Writing self-efficacy average mean score of the participants are at the Agree Level, with a mean of 3.41 ($SD = 1.01$). While the highest mean score 3.74 ($SD= 1.15$) was obtained from the item 5, namely, When I cannot write something in English, I try to solve the problem instead of giving up at the Agree Level, the lowest mean score 3.01 ($SD= 1.08$) was obtained from the item 7, namely, I need help when doing activities related to writing in English at the Somewhat Agree Level which is an expected result because of being a reverse code item. The results remark that the participants have a good level of writing self-efficacy beliefs.

The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the items regarding the subscale listening are given in Table 5.

Table 5: Arithmetic Mean and Standard Deviations Obtained for Each Item Regarding Listening

Item	Listening	Mean	SD
1	I can understand spoken English	3.50	.98
2	I can figure out the main idea of speaking English that I listen to	3.18	1.04
3	I can understand the emotional highlights in a sentence that I listen to	3.60	1.06
4	I can guess the meaning of the words that I do not know when listening to an English speech	2.78	.99
5	I can answer questions about what I hear after hearing an English speech	3.14	.97
6	I can understand what I listen to when watching English TV channels / movies	3.39	1.02
7	When I listen to an English speech, I can distinguish casual and formal language	3.58	1.18
8	I can write correctly what I hear when listening to an English reading passage	3.02	1.05
9	I can understand a short English conversation between two people	3.72	1.06
10	I believe that I will be successful in listening sections of English exams	2.93	1.01
Average		3.29	1.08

According to the data obtained from the subscale, listening, and given in Table 4, self-efficacy average mean score of the participants are at the Somewhat Agree Level, with a mean of 3.29 ($SD = 1.08$). This shows that the participants have a moderate level of self-efficacy beliefs regarding listening skills. Although the mean score of the item 4,

namely, *I can guess the meaning of the words that I do not know when listening to an English speech* is the lowest, it is also at the moderate level (2.61 – 3.40 = Somewhat Agree). Additionally, the self-efficacy scores of the participants for the item1, namely, *I can understand spoken English* with a mean of 3.50 (SD= .98), for the item 3, namely, *I can understand the emotional highlights in a sentence that I listen to* with a mean of 3.60 (SD= 1.06), for the item 7, namely, *When I listen to an English speech, I can distinguish casual and formal language* with a mean of 3.58 (SD= 1.18), and for the item 9, namely, *I can understand a short English conversation between two people* with a mean of 3.72 (SD= 1.06) are at the Agree Level which means that they are pretty good at both understanding emotional highlights and short conversations and distinguishing casual and formal languages in listening.

The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the items regarding the subscale speaking are presented in Table 6.

The data obtained from the subscale, speaking and given in Table 6 show that self-efficacy average mean score of the participants is at the Somewhat Agree Level, with a mean of 3.33 (SD = 1.09) indicating that the participants have a moderate level of self-efficacy beliefs regarding speaking skills. Although all the mean scores belonging to this subscale are at the Somewhat Agree Level, the item 6, namely, *I can speak English in a way that a native English speaker can understand* has the lowest score with a mean of 2.89 (SD= 1.22), and the item 1, namely, *I can meet my needs in daily life using English (Considering that you are abroad, location-direction finding, shopping, etc.)* has the highest one with a mean of 3.82(SD= 1.08). Accordingly, it can be inferred from the results that the participants have a medium level of self-efficacy beliefs regarding speaking skills.

Table 6: Arithmetic Mean and Standard Deviations Obtained for Each Item Regarding Speaking

Item	Speaking	Mean	SD
1	I can meet my needs in daily life using English (Considering that you are abroad, location-direction finding, shopping, etc.).	3.82	1.08
2	In an interview, I can express myself in English. (Entrance to university, Job application etc.)	3.16	1.04
3	According to the purpose and situation, I can speak English in a formal or informal way	3.21	1.03
4	I can respond to the questions asked in English	3.56	.99
5	I can express my thoughts differently when someone does not understand me	3.38	.97
6	I can speak English in a way that a native English speaker can understand	2.89	1.22
Average		3.33	1.09

On the other hand, to find out whether English self-efficacy beliefs of preparatory students regarding reading, writing, listening and speaking skills vary according to

variables such as gender, graduated high school, reasons for university preference and the order of preference or not, statistical analyses were performed using SPSS v.18.0. First, the homogeneity of the variance was tested in the comparison of the gender variable of the data and the t-test was used because the distribution was normal. For the variables “graduated high school”, “reasons for university preference” and “the order of preference”, after testing the homogeneity of the variance, One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used when the distribution was normal and Kruskal Wallis H (KWH) test was used when the distribution was not normal.

With regard to the gender differences, both female (N=91) and male (N= 26) participants exhibited high level of self-efficacy beliefs. Although females obtained higher scores (Mean=14.08; SD= 2.81) than did their counterparts (Mean=15.65; SD= 2.43), there were no statistically significant differences [$p>.05$] between the groups (See Table 7 in Appendix). Additionally, although male participants have slightly higher scores from reading (Mean =4.11; SD=.71), writing (Mean =3.42; SD=.75), listening (Mean =3.80; SD=.98), and speaking (Mean =4.30; SD=.97), than their counterparts' reading (Mean =3.85; SD=.85), writing (Mean =3.13; SD=.93), listening (Mean =3.41; SD=.96), and speaking (Mean =3.68; SD=1.07), there was only a statistically significant difference for the listening skill between the groups favoring the male participants ($p<0.05$).

Related to the graduated high school, reasons for university preference and the order of preference variables, the results showed that there were no statistically significant differences [$p>.05$] among the groups (See Tables 8, 9, 10, 11 and, 12 in Appendix).

4. Discussion

In general, the purpose of this study, conducted in four phases, was to evaluate the effects of self-efficacy beliefs of preparatory students studying English as a foreign language at a university on their existing capacities and abilities for organizing and implementing the behaviors that are expected from them in order to cope with learning difficulties, development of foreign language skills and professional preparation. The first phase encompassed the meta analytic study and aimed to investigate both the effects of self-efficacy beliefs on the development of listening, reading, writing and speaking skills of the students studying English as a foreign language and the effects of EFL programs on self-efficacy beliefs of EFL students. When the data concerning the self-efficacy beliefs and effects on four language skills were evaluated according to the random effect models, in the meta-analytic procedure, the effect size value was found to

be 0.958. This value was indicated as a large level of compliance according to Thalheimer and Cook's (2002) classification and therefore, it can be inferred that the effect size level of self-efficacy beliefs on a foreign language learning /teaching is high. This substantial result was coherent with the effect coefficients of the studies included in the analysis (i.e., Alimoradi, Jahandar, & Khodabandehlou, 2013; Aregu, 2013; Balaman Uçar, 2016; Baleghizadeh & Masoun, 2013; Ekiz, 2013; Gol & Aaleabbas, 2016; Karimi, 2011; Kassem, 2013; Khanmohammad & Eilaghi, 2013; Noroozi & Mehrdad, 2016; Semiz, 2011; Yavuz Erkan, 2004; and Zareian, Adel & Noghani, 2015). Additionally, similar results were consistent with the outcomes of the various studies conducted nationally and internationally (Coşkun & Ghaemi, 2015; Lin, 2015; Rathert, 2013; Salehi & Khalaji, 2014) and excluded from the analysis.

The second phase, qualitative part, of the study included the participants' views that were available in the included studies on the factors affecting their self-efficacy beliefs in a foreign language learning /teaching through document analysis by generating the themes and codes. The responses were categorized as the factors affecting foreign language students' self-efficacy beliefs positively and negatively. Related codes were created based on the emergent themes. The most striking codes for the factors affecting students' self-efficacy beliefs positively were stated as "seeing learning English as a future goal," "wish of living abroad," and "receiving positive feedback from teachers on their constantly increasing skills" which were supported in previous research results (Semiz, 2011; Özkasap, 2009). Self-efficacy beliefs of students enhance provided that their academic achievements are high (Jahanian & Mahjoubi, 2013; Yavuzer & Koç, 2002). Therefore, if students' increasing skills are noticed by teachers, students will give more credit to themselves for success. Apart from positively affecting factors, some factors affecting self-efficacy beliefs negatively were discussed under three sub-themes as factors stemming from students, stemming from outside of students, and stemming from teachers' performance (from teachers' own perspectives). The most remarkable codes that were almost involved in all the three subthemes were expressed as "fear of being caught while making mistakes", "insufficient listening and speaking lessons", and "having the idea that learning from a foreigner is more instructive". Based on the views of the participants in the included studies, it can be inferred that both EFL students and teachers share the same difficulties regarding listening and speaking skills and the fear of making mistakes. Similarly, Hamouda (2013) remarked that most teachers do not seem to pay attention listening and speaking skills while designing their lessons. They believe that these skills will develop naturally within the process of language learning. On the other hand, the instructors' fear of making mistakes stems from the fear of failure and it has a very big

effect on instructors' academic life. In Karakaya's (2011) study non-native foreign language instructors stated that they felt nervous when they spoke English in front of the other language teachers in an academic environment. Çubukçu (2008) also revealed that although EFL instructors had high self-efficacy levels, they were afraid of making mistakes or they might be feeling shy to express themselves in front of their colleagues. The third phase, qualitative part, of the study included the views of the preparatory students studying English Language Teaching and English Language and Literature (N= 58) studying at Cumhuriyet University School of Foreign Languages on their existing capacities and abilities for organizing and implementing the behaviors that are expected from them toward English in order to cope with learning difficulties, development of foreign language skills and professional preparation. Four themes were identified as (1) The suitability of English language level that the students have already had for a preparatory class (2) The use of the four skills equally, (3) Problems stemming from teachers and students and, (4) Suggestions. The emergent subthemes related to the first theme, namely, "the suitability of English language level that the students have already had for a preparatory class" were "Positive views stemming from having the ability to successfully accomplish the required academic tasks" and "Negative views stemming from the feeling of having inadequate English." The most prominent codes associated with positive views were "Being willing to enhance their knowledge of English", "Loving English" and, "Having the necessary knowledge and skills to accomplish English successfully in preparatory class". These codes showed the consistency with the literature regarding the positive effects of self -efficacy beliefs on foreign language learning /teaching environment (Chen, 2007; Hashemi & Ghanizadeh, 2011; Pajares, 2002; Wang & Pape, 2007). Similarly, Jabbarifar (2011) emphasizes that high self-efficacy is accompanied by improved academic achievement and performance. The most striking codes regarding the negative views for the first theme, the suitability of English language level that the students have already had for a preparatory class, were: "Insufficient education due to being given much more weight to the grammar lessons than the other ones" and "Insufficient opportunities to speak English in lectures". Similarly, recent results (i.e. Güvendir, 2017; and, Sönmez Ektem & Yıldız, 2017) have supported a causal relationship between disruptions in foreign language education and a low level of self-efficacy toward learning English. In this regard, Rocío (2012) emphasizes that the great majority of the time in the classroom is used to go into grammar and there is no usually time to devote to other interaction activities. Moreover, in most of the cases, the English language is not used during the English lesson but also mother tongue is used. On the other hand, Cook (2001), and Nation (2003) encourage the use English in an EFL classroom and warn that using the mother

tongue in the classroom reduces the amount of input and the opportunity of practice. The emergent theme “the use of the four skills equally” is also strongly implied by many language theoreticians. They claim that all features of language interrelate and intermix and therefore, students should be fostered to use all aspects of language, namely, listening, speaking, reading, and writing simultaneously in significant, functional, and collective activities (Farris & Kaczmariski, 1988). The most prominent codes that reflect negative thoughts regarding the use of the four skills equally were “not given equal weight to each skill in schools during their education”, “insufficient time allocation for each skill” and, “not being exposed to native speaker teachers of English”. In this regard, researches also show that not all the time the integration of all language skills is equally applied as of utmost importance. Around the world, some curricula and textbooks, quite often, tend to focus on just one of the four skills of English as foreign language, mostly to the exclusion of the others (Brown, 2007). Furthermore, Rabbit (2015) emphasizes that although exposure to all domains of English holds equal importance because each can accelerate the acquisition of language skills in the other’s domain, a large number of students struggle to engage in English enough. On the other hand, it is interesting to notice that one of the codes reflecting the participants’ negative thoughts, “not being exposed to native speaker teachers of English” shows consistency with the code emerged during the thematic analysis from the views of the participants of the studies included in this study. However, it seems acceptable for native teachers to be awarded ‘authenticity and authority’ (Amin, 1997, p. 386) and for a teacher without the requisite language skills to be treated as crucially lacking authority and self-confidence in the classroom (Cullen, 2001). The theme “problems stemming from teachers and students” was consistent with the themes emerged during the thematic analysis and discussed above and with the previous research results (Ekiz, 2013; Semiz, 2011; Özkasap, 2009; Rathert, 2013; Ünyılmaz, 2014). The last theme included suggestions expected from teachers. The most remarkable codes were aligned as “teachers should choose listening or reading material that interests students and will hold their attention”, “more emphasis on speaking and listening activities” and, “struggling students should be encouraged to take extra effort”. Suggestions regarding the material selection based on suitability of content and exploitability are consistent with literature generally (Angell, DuBravac & Gonglewski, 2008; Berardo, 2006; Canagarajah, 2006; Edge & Garton, 2009; Gilmore, 2007; Mohan & Beckett; 2003; Richards, 2006; Rostami & Mahdavi Zafarghandi, 2014). In this regard, Harwood (2010) indicates that very often teachers do not choose their own coursebook or other materials, because in many contexts they are prescribed at a higher level, for example by the institution’s administration or by a Ministry of Education. Therefore,

course materials may sometimes have no interest to students and they might be bored. It may also be the case that the level of the materials does not match that of the students (Little, Devitt & Singleton, 1995).

The fourth phase of the study included descriptive analysis. While English Self Efficacy Beliefs of the participants for reading and writing skills were found at the Agree Level (3.41 – 4.20) on the 5 –point Likert scale, with a mean of 3.59(*SD* = .97) and 3.41 (*SD*= 1.01) respectively, their listening and speaking skills were found at the Somewhat Agree Level (2.61– 3.40) with a mean of 3.29 (*SD*= 1.08) and 3.33 (*SD*= 1.09) respectively. This result shows that while the English self-efficacy beliefs of the participants for reading and writing skills are at good levels, their English self-efficacy beliefs for listening and speaking skills are at moderate levels. These descriptive results are coherent with the qualitative results of the study in which related themes and codes emerged from the participants' views reflecting their insufficient skills as listening and speaking. Similarly, Büyükduman (2006), revealed in her study that while English preservice teachers' self- efficacy beliefs regarding writing and reading skills were high, their most inadequate skills were listening and speaking. In Hamouda's (2013) study, students assessed their reading and writing abilities as "good", and their speaking and listening as "poor". They were not satisfied with the instruction of speaking and listening. Moreover, some students thought listening instruction was 'below average' or 'poor'. Memduhoğlu and Çelik (2015) also studied self-efficacy beliefs of university students studying English Language Teaching and English Language and Literature and collected data with the same scale developed by Yanar and Bümen (2012) and used in this study. They found the same results, namely, the foreign language students had a medium level of self-efficacy beliefs and their self-efficacy beliefs toward reading skill was higher than their listening and speaking skills. The results regarding the gender, graduated high school, order of preference at the university admission, and reasons for preference variables showed no statistically significant difference among the groups (See Appendix). Similarly, some researchers (i.e. Alimoradi, Jahandar & Khodabandehlou, 2013; Salehi & Khalaji, 2014; Semiz, 2011) found no significant differences between male and female in their self-efficacy beliefs and among high school type they graduated (i.e. Memduhoğlu & Çelik, 2015).

5. Implications

This study is a combination of the results of Meta-analysis, Statistical analysis and thematic analysis used within the scope of methodological pluralism that provides a more balanced perspective with abundance of data toward holism (Asif 2013). In

general, the quantitative results of the study suggest that while self-efficacy beliefs on a foreign language learning /teaching is high, in terms of using the four skills, listening and speaking are the ones that the participants exhibit the weakest self-efficacy beliefs respectively. When the qualitative results from Maxqda analysis were evaluated, it seems that the results are consistent with the quantitative results of this study. Accordingly, the first remarkable implication derives from the methodological process of this research that provides much needed data obtained from both national and international studies as quantitatively and qualitatively on the self-efficacy beliefs and their effects on English learning/teaching as a foreign or second language. A second implication stems from the findings that point to evidence that foreign language learners have lower self-efficacy beliefs on listening and speaking skills than reading and writing skills. A third implication derives from the finding on studying almost exclusively with a grammar-based approach. This study revealed that many participants taken part in the phases of this study imply that although they have been exposed to grammar-oriented English learning/teaching for many years and could recite the grammar by heart, they have hesitated too much to browse through all the grammar rules in their heads before making an utterance. However, the teaching and learning of grammar has always been one of the most hotly debated topics in the field of language education. According to Larsen-Freeman (2001), “grammar is to be seen as a skill not as a competence” (p. 67). If grammar as a method of language teaching and learning within the so-called grammar oriented approach, is expected as the fifth skill, it is the backbone of a language and essential in order to master a language (Foppoli, 2017).

Another implication of the present study is that it provides findings on having more respect for native English speaking teachers and the desire for studying with them due to not being exposed to study with a native English speaking teacher. The findings also revealed that although the demand for native English speaking teachers is so high among university students, hiring native English speaking teachers at universities is rare. However, given an equal opportunity to well qualified native and nonnative English speaking teachers will allow learners to have access to such teachers as competent language users (Lee, 2005).

6. Suggestions for Future Research

The results of the study present some suggestions for further research. Due to the insufficiency in the quantitative data of the studies that have been examined for inclusion in the meta-analysis, it seems necessary to conduct experimental studies to

investigate the construct of self-efficacy and its effects on foreign language learners. Therefore, instead of short term bases studies conducted by questionnaires or surveys, studies in which self-efficacy is examined over long-term periods are suggested. It is also suggested perform longitudinal studies to observe the differences occurring in the self-efficacy beliefs of foreign language students at specific time intervals. Additionally, in service teacher development programs are suggested for nonnative English speaking teachers to improve especially their listening and speaking qualifications and to reflect their demonstrable language proficiency perfectly in the classroom.

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Note: Studies marked with asterisk (*) are included in the meta-analysis

Appendix

Table 7: Independent Groups t-test Scores of the Participants in terms of Gender Variable

The English Self Efficacy Beliefs Scale	N 117	Male (n= 26; 22.2%)		Female (n= 91; 77.8 %)		T & P Values		Levene's Test	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	t	P	F	P
Overall Scale		15.65	2.43	14.08	2.81	2.573	.011	.361	.549
Reading		4.11	.711	3.85	.850	1.412	.161	.707	.402
Writing		3.42	.757	3.13	.933	1.458	.148	.164	.687
Listening		3.80	.980	3.41	.966	1.809	.073	.031	.861
Speaking		4.30	.970	3.68	1.07	2.677	.009	1.062	.305

Table 8: The KWH Test Results According to Graduated High School Variable

	Graduated High School	N	Mean Rank	SD	KWH	P	MWU
Overall Scale	Anatolian Teacher High School	6	46.33				
	Anatolian High School	89	60.22	3	1.016	.797	-
	Anatolian Technical-Vocational High School	9	58.11				
	Regular High School	13	57.08				
<i>Levene's Test = .127 P = .001</i>							
Reading	Anatolian Teacher High School	6	61.17				
	Anatolian High School	89	57.10	3	2.724	.436	-
	Anatolian Technical-Vocational High School	9	75.06				
	Regular High School	13	59.92				
<i>Levene's Test = .296 P = .000</i>							
Writing	Anatolian Teacher High School	6	49.42				
	Anatolian High School	89	60.28	3	3.064	.382	-
	Anatolian Technical-Vocational High School	9	44.39				
	Regular High School	13	64.81				
<i>Levene's Test = .278 P = .000</i>							
Listening	Anatolian Teacher High School	6	55.33				
	Anatolian High School	89	59.64	3	.254	.968	-
	Anatolian Technical-Vocational High School	9	59.89				
	Regular High School	13	55.69				
<i>Levene's Test = .227 P = .000</i>							
Speaking	Anatolian Teacher High School	6	41.67				
	Anatolian High School	89	62.03	3	3.723	.293	-
	Anatolian Technical-Vocational High School	9	49.67				
	Regular High School	13	52.69				
<i>Levene's Test = .230 P = .000</i>							

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Table 9: The Variance Analysis (ANOVA) Results According to Order of Preference Variable

Overall scale						
Preference Order	N	M	SD	F	P	LSD
	117					
1-5		14.82	3.00			–
6-10		14.62	2.61	1.122	.329	
11 and above		13.97	2.80			
Levene's Test	F=.180	P= .835; P>0.05				

Table 10: The KWH Test Results According to Order of Preference Variable

SubDimensions	Order of preference	N	Mean Rank	SD	KWH	P	MWU
Reading	1-5	45	61.18				
	6-10	24	63.94	2	.899	.638	–
	11 and above	48	54.49				
<i>Levene's Test = .303 P = .000</i>							
Writing	1-5	45	66.89				
	6-10	24	50.33	2	1.803	.406	–
	11 and above	48	55.94				
<i>Levene's Test = .260 P = .000</i>							
Listening	1-5	45	65.78				
	6-10	24	59.31	2	3.910	.142	–
	11 and above	48	52.49				
<i>Levene's Test = .252 P = .000</i>							
Speaking	1-5	45	56.78				
	6-10	24	68.17	2	2.409	.300	–
	11 and above	48	56.50				
<i>Levene's Test = .256 P = .000</i>							

Table 11: The Variance Analysis (ANOVA) Results According to Reasons for Preference Variable

Overall scale							
Reason for Preference	N	M	SD	F	P	LSD	
	117						
My choice	84	14.63	2.69				
My parents' choice	7	13.57	2.43				
Having a job guarantee	12	13.08	2.50	1.410	.244	–	
In order not to be idle	14	14.85	53.61				
Levene's Test	F=1.196	P= .315; P>0.05					

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Table 12: The KWH Test Results According to Reasons for Preference Variable

Subdimensions	Reasons for preference	N	Mean Rank	SD	KWH	P	MWU
Reading	Being my choice	84	59.38				
	Being my family's choice	7	66.93	3	.768	.857	—
	Having a job guarantee	12	56.29				
	In order not to be idle	14	55.07				
<i>Levene's Test = .290 P= .000</i>							
Writing	Being my choice	84	62.00				
	Being my family's choice	7	43.86	3	3.587	.310	—
	Having a job guarantee	12	49.17				
	In order not to be idle	14	57.00				
<i>Levene's Test = .273 P= .000</i>							
Listening	Being my choice	84	61.40				
	Being my family's choice	7	55.71	3	1.622	.114	—
	Having a job guarantee	12	31.63				
	In order not to be idle	14	69.68				
<i>Levene's Test = .222 P= .000</i>							
Speaking	Being my choice	84	59.88				
	Being my family's choice	7	39.29	3	3.868	.276	—
	Having a job guarantee	12	54.33				
	In order not to be idle	14	67.57				
<i>Levene's Test = .341 P= .000</i>							

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